

APPLICATION OF A MEMORY DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY IN THE STUDY OF VOCABULARY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: The modern education system lays the foundations for favorable development for all students. In psychology, attention has always been paid to such important tasks as: development of mental processes, overcoming poor progress, optimization of the learning process. The development of mental processes has been a prerequisite for successful learning at school. Memory allows you to accumulate and preserve experience. A lot of attention is paid to the study of memory at preschool and school age.

Keywords: function, memory, experience, memory, potential, vocabulary, method

Memory occupies a special place in the structure of the psyche: it has been somehow integrated into all mental cognitive processes - and therefore received the status of a "general organic function." Memory provides the processes of preserving individual experience, as well as genetically determined mechanisms for transmitting information.

To date, there are several definitions of the concept of "memory". A.V. Petrovsky, R.S. Nemov, A.G. Maklakov define memory as a mental cognitive process. It should be noted that the definitions are almost identical: A.V. Petrovsky argues that "memory is the memorization, preservation and subsequent reproduction by the individual of his experience." A.G. Maklakov: "By memory we understand the imprinting, preservation, subsequent recognition and reproduction of traces of past experience." [11, p. 50]

R.S. Nemov gives several definitions: "... the ability to receive, store and reproduce life experience" and the second, more precise and strict, from his point of

view: "... psychophysiological and cultural processes that perform the functions of remembering, preserving and reproducing information in life". [10, c. 156.]

Thus, it can be concluded that all the above definitions are based on the basic processes of memory, all authors focus on memorization and reproduction, with some discrepancy in the mention of "recognition". R.S. Nemov simultaneously notes the psychophysiological and cultural specificity of memory processes.

The above researchers draw attention to the role of memory processes in human life: memory "separates a person from the animal kingdom and ... is a condition for successful adaptation" (RS Nemov); "ensures the unity and integrity of the individual" (A.V. Petrovsky); "represents a |end-to-end| process that ensures the continuity of mental processes and unites all cognitive processes into a single whole| (A.G. Maklakov).

The manifestations of memory are distinguished by a wide variety of forms, which is due to the fact that memory, one way or another, accompanies all kinds of diverse human activities.

The study of a foreign language develops different aspects of the personality: memory, attention, diligence, language guess, erudition, discipline; makes the child more active; accustoms him to collective forms of work in a group; awakens curiosity, artistry, shapes the child intellectually and aesthetically. In addition, there is a real opportunity to identify children capable of languages at an early stage and prepare them for further serious study of a foreign language.

Any language has represented by phonetic, grammatical and lexical material, and the study of this language consists directly in mastering this material by mastering the main types of speech activity. And although the teaching of the phonetic, grammatical and lexical aspects of the English language to younger students is carried out in close relationship, based on the physical, psychological and intellectual characteristics of children of this age, it can be argued that the process of teaching vocabulary is fundamental for them.

So, at the initial level of teaching a foreign language, the main emphasis is on developing children's understanding of spoken English and laying the foundations of pronunciation:

- complete perception is developed through the constant use of elementary English words;
- phrases and speech clichés are memorized from songs and poems;
- recognition and use of simple words occurs during the game.

The number of words, speech clichés, and lexical topics presented for study vary depending on each training course or individual teacher program. However, there are certain criteria for the selection of lexical material for children of preschool age:

- all words studied at this stage should mean concepts that are well known to the child in their native language;
- words should have frequent use in the language and great compatibility with each other.[17, c. 59].

At the present stage of development of school education, one of the most urgent problems is the need for a qualitative improvement in the knowledge of the English language with a small number of hours of study load allotted for the study of this subject by the school curriculum, only 1-2 lessons per week in primary grades, but first of all, to develop personality potential.

The process of learning a foreign language provides for the development of the following communication skills: speaking, listening, reading and writing, as well as the development of the necessary lexical, grammatical, phonetic and graphic skills. Let us dwell on the lexical side of foreign language speech.

In the methodology of teaching a foreign language, namely its lexical side, it is proposed to use the game teaching method, as quite interesting and effective in organizing the learning activities of students. The game is one of the techniques in teaching a foreign language, which is especially often used at the junior level of education. With the help of the game, a natural communicative game is created that

arouses the interest and activity of children, and the element of competition that is constantly present in the game, the desire to win, mobilizes the attention of students, trains their memory.

All this contributes to a stronger assimilation of the lexical material being studied.

Lexical games have the following goals:

- introduce students to new words and their combinations;
- to train students in the use of vocabulary in situations close to the natural environment;
- to activate the speech-thinking activity of students;
- develop a speech response.

When studying vocabulary, special attention is paid to the system of exercises recommended for practicing and consolidating lexical material at the initial stage of learning English. In the system of exercises that develop any type of speech activity, two subsystems are distinguished - preparatory exercises and speech exercises. When teaching English, one should talk about the use of preparatory exercises.

Obviously, one of the important problems that exist in the methodology of teaching foreign languages is the problem of organizing training using a game methodology. The use of the game in foreign language lessons is important for the acquisition of new ideas or the formation of new skills and abilities. The game is of great importance for the development of the motivational-need sphere of the student. Thus, the pedagogical potential of any game is to arouse interest among schoolchildren, stimulate their mental and speech activity aimed at consolidating new lexical units, create an atmosphere of rivalry and cooperation during the performance of a particular exercise.

The vocabulary of the English language is a very important element in learning the language. Only with a larger active stock will the child be able to master grammatical structures. When choosing lexical material, it is necessary to take into account its communicative significance for children, objective complexity. When

teaching younger students, great attention should be paid to the use of visual and illustrative material, however, when it comes to organizing a role-playing game, simulating actions when executing commands, or illustrating poems.

Thus, we came to the conclusion that the use of a memory development strategy in the study of vocabulary is an effective method of teaching English, students perceive new material much deeper and this causes them a wide interest than a simple lesson without using any information technology.

REFERENCES:

1. Аникеева Н.П. Воспитание игрой: книга для учителя. - М.: Просвещение, 1987. - 143 с.

2. Абрамов Г.С. Практикум по возрастной психологии: Учеб. Пособие для студ. ВУЗов. - 2-е изд., Стереотип / Г.С. Абрамова - М.: Издательский центр Академия, 1992. - 320 с.

3. Боровикова Е.Г. Наглядная программа для младших школьников, изучающих английский язык, и их родителей. Проблемы, поиски, решения // Иностранные языки в школе - 2003. - №2 - 23 с.

4. Гальскова Н.Д., Гез Н.И. Теория обучения иностранным языкам. Лингводидактика и методика / Н.Д. Гальскова, Н.И. Гез - М.: Издательский центр " Академия", 2005. - 336 с.

5. Негневицкая Е.И. иностранный язык для самых маленьких: вчера, сегодня, завтра // Иностранные языки в школе. - 1987. - №6. - 26 с.

6. Щебедина В.В. "Обучение детей английской разговорной речи" // Иностранные языки в школе - 1997. - №2 - 58 с.

7. Щерба Л.В. Преподавание иностранного языка в школе. Общие вопросы методики.- М.: просвещение, 1947.- 129 с.

1. 8. Jumaev U. S. Socio-psychological features of international and intercultural relations of humanity //Journal of Pedagogical Excellence. – 2019. – №. 4. – С. 112-117.

2. Жумаев У. С. Глобалізація і культура народів //Вісник Харківського національного педагогічного університету імені ГС Сковороди. Психологія. – 2012. – №. 43 (1). – С. 90-97.
3. Jumayev U. TOŹSAMOŚĆ NARODOWA JAKO PROBLEM PSYCHOLOGII SPOŁECZNEJ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4.
4. Jumayev U. ШЕСТЬ ПОДХОДОВ К ПОНИМАНИЮ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ КУЛЬТУР: КУЛЬТУРНЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ХОФСТЕДЕ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 22. – №. 22.
5. Jumayev U. Uncertain Stereotypes and the Intellectual Brain: Knowledge and Culture in the Perception of A “One-Sided” Person //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 3.
6. Jumayev U. ГЛОБАЛІШАВУВ ШАРОИТИДА ОММАВИЙ МАДАНИЯТНИНГ ЖАМИЯТ ҲАЁТИГА ТАЪСИРИНИ ИЖТИМОЙ ПСИХОЛОГИК ТАДҚИҚИ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2020. – Т. 4. – №. 4.
7. Жумаев У. С. АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ И ПРОБЛЕМА ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ МЕЖКУЛЬТУРНОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ //Рекомендовано к печати Ученым советом Института психологии имени ГС Костюка НАПН Украины (Протокол № 14 от 28 декабря 2020). – 2020. – С. 47.
8. Jumayev U. The Study Of The Psychological Properties Of Computer Technologies And The Impact Of The Internet In The Development Of Adolescent Consciousness And Thinking //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 3.
9. Jumayev U. СОЦИОКУЛЬТУРНАЯ СРЕДА И ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ЗДОРОВЬЕ ЛИЧНОСТИ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1.

10. Sattorovich J. U. Intercultural difference parameters: Hofstede and Trompenaars theories //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences. – 2020. – T. 8. – №. 11. – C. 115-124.
11. Sattorovich J. U. Psychological study of the impact of computer technology and the Internet on the development of adolescent consciousness and thinking //Eurasian Medical Research Periodical. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 31-41.
12. Sattorovich J. U. Intercultural Communication: Concept, Essence and Theories of Intercultural Communication //International Journal on Integrated Education. – T. 3. – №. 11. – C. 1-4.
13. Sattorovich J. U. An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal //ACADEMICIA. – C. 151.
14. Sobirovich T. B. A study of national and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 5. – C. 417-421.
15. Sobirovich T. B. Interethnic Harmony And Religious Tolerance-An Integral Part of The Ancient Traditions Of The Uzbeks.
16. Turdiev B. S. EVOLUTION OF IDEAS AND VIEWS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY AND SPIRITUAL RENEWALS //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2020. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 209-217.
17. Sobirovich T. B., Ikrom o'g'li I. M. ISSUE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIETY IN THE VIEWS OF EASTERN THINKERS //" ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM. – 2022. – C. 111-114.
18. Sobirovich T. B. National and universal principles of democracy //Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 12. – №. 1. – C. 334-338.